

INCREASED INTERFACE STRENGTH IN CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES THROUGH A ZnO NANOWIRE INTERPHASE

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SUMMARY

A novel nanocomposite is developed with ZnO nanowires grown on the surface of the reinforcing fiber for an enhanced interface. Experimental testing shows that the growth does not adversely affect fiber strength; interfacial shear strength is significantly increased by 113% and the lamina shear strength and modulus are increased by 37.8% and 38.8%.

Keywords: Composite Materials, Zinc Oxide, Nanowires, Functional Coatings, Hybrid Materials

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past few decades, the manufacturing processes and our knowledge base for predicting the bulk mechanical response of fiber reinforced composite materials has matured. The rapid development and progress of composites technology has been spawned by the high specific strength, stiffness, and toughness offered with respect to other engineering materials. However, the performance of a fiber reinforced composite material is influenced by a variety of parameters and each fiber and matrix typically offers contrasting advantages and disadvantages that must be weighed to fulfill a specific application. Furthermore, a composite made from a strong fiber and a well-suited matrix may not necessarily result in a strong material because the fiber-matrix interface is equally important in determining the mechanical performance of the composite.^[1] Ultimately the successful development of a composite material is defined by the quality of the interface.

In composites, interfacial adhesion between the fiber and matrix is typically improved by enhancing the chemical interaction with the matrix or by increasing the fiber surface area, in order to provide a larger area over which to transfer load. Oxidative surface treatments typically add functional groups, remove weak outer layers of the fiber, and texture the fiber surface to increase the interfacial surface area. Nonoxidative treatments involve the deposition of materials on the fiber surface, such as whiskers to enhance load transfer and bonding. In “whiskerization,” single crystals of silicon carbide or silicon nitride are grown on the surface of the fiber. Rabotnov *et al.*^[2] and Kowbel *et al.*^[3] demonstrated improvements of 200%-300% in interlaminar shear strength for carbon/epoxy and carbon/carbon composites, respectively. Improvements

were attributed to through-thickness reinforcement and increased interfacial area. Rabotonov indicated that uniform distribution of whiskers offered maximum improvement.^[2] However, the significant improvements in interlaminar properties came at the expense of the in-plane properties, which degraded due to damage of the carbon fiber surface due to high-temperature (1300–1800°C) exposure and whisker growth conditions. Thostenson *et al.*^[4] grew carbon nanotubes (CNTs) on the surface of carbon fibers and measured only a 15% increase in shear strength due to degradation of the fiber when exposed to the catalyst and chemical vapor deposition environment (also see^[5-6]). Bekyarova *et al.*^[7] later used low temperature electrodeposition of CNTs on carbon fibers to avoid damage to the fiber, but results showed low density and non-uniform coatings that had limited impact on interface strength. Other methods to improve the toughness of fiber reinforced composites, such as interleave materials offer enhanced load transfer between plies to reduced delamination but do not address the fiber matrix interface and reduce the fiber volume fraction ultimately decreasing the composites in-plane strength.

Prior efforts that have investigated whiskerization or interleave approaches to increase the interfacial strength of a composite material have gained toughness at the expense of the in-plane properties of the composite. The decrease in strength has typically occurred due to weakening of the carbon fiber during high temperature processing, fiber reaction with catalysts, or a decrease in fiber volume fraction through additional matrix filler. To circumvent these issues, we have utilized a low temperature (<90°C) solution based growth technique for the formation of ZnO nanowires on the surface of carbon fibers. Since the ZnO nanowires are rigid they protrude into the matrix materials and increase load transfer between the fiber and matrix. Additionally, the ZnO nanowires could also be used to add functionality due to the piezoelectric and semiconductor properties of ZnO which make them well suited for gas sensors^[8-9], solar cells^[10-12], light emitting diodes^[13-14], dynamic sensors^[15] and energy harvesting materials.^[16-17]

We have demonstrated that the solution based growth of ZnO nanowires allows the nanowires to be directly grown on carbon fiber in tows or fabrics. This process uses a ZnO nanoparticle seed for the growth of nanowires which can be applied to the surface of the fibers through dip coating or electrophoretic deposition.^[18-19] The formation of wires (aspect ratio >10) occurs at pH values between 9 and 12 without the use of additives;^[20-22] however, with pH values from 5-9, wires will form in the presence of hexamethylenetetramine (HMTA). Variation of the solution's molar concentration, pH, temperature, and exposure time allows for control over the length, diameter and spatial density of the wires.^[23] No other research efforts have been found in the literature that have studied the use of ZnO nanowires to enhance the interface strength of materials. Here we will demonstrate that this process allows the nanowires to be readily grown on carbon fibers, tows or fabrics for strength enhancement. The nanowire growth time can also be decreased by more than 35 times through the use of an electric field.^[24] This significantly decreased growth time is compatible with large scale manufacturing processes indicating the potential to transition this technology to practice.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ZnO nanowires were grown on a tow of IM7 carbon fibers that were seeded and then immersed in the growth solution. Fig. 1a-1c shows SEM images of the resulting ZnO nanowires grown on a tow of IM7 carbon fiber. Note the uniformity of the

nanowire growth along the carbon fiber and full coverage of several fibers. This standard method for the formation of nanowires results in nanowires with aspect ratios up to 50, while higher aspect ratios can be generated by introducing a molecule that inhibits radial growth of the wires but allows axial growth.^[10] The addition of low-molecular-weight poly(ethylenimine) (PEI) to the solution results in the growth of wires with aspect ratios greater than 125.

Figure 1. ZnO nanowires grown on carbon fiber with scale bar lengths of (a) 27.8 μm , (b) 3 μm , (c) 500 nm.

2.1. Single Fiber Tensile Testing

In order to demonstrate the significant strength enhancement that can occur through the use of a ZnO nanowire interface, single fiber tensile, single fiber segmentation testing and V-notch shear testing (ASTM D 5379)^[25] have been performed. The first test was single fiber tensile testing and was used to demonstrate the effect of the nanowire growth process on the strength of the fiber, which dictates the in-plane properties of the composite.

Figure 2. Single fiber tensile testing of carbon fibers, (a) experimental testing apparatus used to measure the stress and strain of the fiber. (b) The resulting tensile strength and strain at failure for each cases of fibers tested and it can be seen that the growth of the ZnO nanowires on the carbon fiber surface and the functionalization procedure result in no decrease in fiber tensile strength.

The resulting stress and strain at failure of the single fiber tensile tests performed on bare and ZnO nanowire coated fibers are plotted in Fig. 2b. The tensile testing results showed a linear response up to failure, consistent with the expected linear elastic

behavior of the fibers. From the results of these tests, it can be seen that the growth of ZnO nanowires on the surface of the fiber does not lead to any discernable decrease in fiber tensile strength. This result indicates that the in-plane properties of a fiber reinforced composite constructed from this material would not decrease as all previous studies have found.^[2-4]

2.2. Single Fiber Fragmentation Testing

Once the strength on the carbon fiber specimens has been identified before and after nanowire growth, the effect of the nanowire coating on the interfacial shear strength of the fiber and matrix can be measured through single fiber fragmentation testing. The single-fiber fragmentation test is a method that is widely used to assess the properties of the fiber/matrix interface. In this test, a single filament is embedded in a dog bone shaped polymer specimen that is loaded while being observed through an optical microscope.^[26-28] As a tensile load is applied to the specimen, stress is transferred to the fiber through shear stresses at the interface. As the applied stress is increased, the fiber reaches its tensile strength and fractures. Because the segmented fiber continues to carry load as the polymer specimen is further strained, the fiber will continue to fracture into shorter segments until a saturation point is reached. At this saturation point, the surface area of each fiber segment can no longer transfer sufficient shear load to the fiber to reach the tensile strength and induce further breaks. At constant fiber diameter and fiber strength, shorter fragment lengths imply a stronger fiber/matrix interface, therefore allowing the interfacial strength to be evaluated for the coated and uncoated fibers. During the fabrication of the segmentation specimens, the wetting properties of the nanowires were characterized with a composites grade epoxy. The cross section of the carbon fiber is shown in Fig. 3 and clearly shows that the epoxy resin can effectively wet the nanowire surface, indicating that the bond area has been significantly increased.

Figure 3. SEM micrograph of the carbon fiber cross section at two scales (a) 4 μ m and (b) 1 μ m. The carbon fiber and epoxy were milled with a Focused Ion Beam demonstrating that the epoxy completely wets the ZnO nanowire coating.

This tensile testing system for single fiber fragmentation testing was designed such that it allows the stress and strain on the specimen to be applied and monitored through an optical microscope. The samples were placed in a screw-driven micro-tensile test stage shown in Fig. 4a. Using this system the number of fragments was measured under increasing strain such that the saturation point could be identified. The inset of Fig. 4a shows an optical micrograph of the fractured fiber. Segmentation tests were performed on bare carbon fibers and carbon fibers with ZnO nanowires grown on the surface. The

strain vs. the number of fragments over a 16 mm sample is plotted in Fig. 4b. It can be seen in the figure that application of a ZnO nanowire interface significantly increases the fracture density in the specimen, which indicates improved fiber/matrix interface strength. From this figure the interfacial shear strength can be calculated to increase from 15.87 MPa for the bare fiber to 33.87 MPa with the ZnO nanowire interface or by 113%. This significant improvement in interfacial shear strength was obtained without any effort to optimize the nanowire properties. Because the spatial density, length and diameter of the nanowires are highly controllable, it is expected that the shear strength can be further increased.

Figure 4. Single fiber fragmentation test used to determine the interfacial shear strength of the nanowire coated carbon fiber. (a) Experimental setup used for testing with the insert depicting a typical fiber fracture in the polymer dog bone specimen. (b) Results of fragmentation testing depicting a significant increase in the fracture density when ZnO nanowires are grown on the fiber surface corresponding to an increase in interfacial shear strength from 15.87 to 33.87 MPa with the ZnO nanowire interface, or 113%.

2.3. V-Notch Shear Testing

The transition of the interfacial shear strength to the shear modulus and strength of a lamina has been evaluated through v-notch shear testing (ASTM 5379).^[25] A lamina is a single layer of the composite without separate plies of reinforcement. The testing results are shown in Fig. 5 for five bare carbon fiber lamina and three ZnO nanowire coated carbon fiber lamina. The testing demonstrates that the significantly increased interfacial properties measured through segmentation testing translate to improved shear properties of the lamina. The stress-strain response of the v-notch shear specimens is shown in Fig. 5a. From the figure it can be clearly seen that the ZnO nanowires lead to significantly increased shear strength and shear modulus. The average shear strength of the lamina increases from 52.9 MPa for the bare carbon fibers to 72.95 MPa for the ZnO nanowire coated fibers, or a 37.5% increase. The average shear modulus, G_{13} , of the lamina shown in Fig. 5b, increases from 2.41 GPa for the bare carbon fibers to 3.34 GPa for the ZnO nanowire coated carbon fibers, or a 38.8% increase. The increased interfacial adhesion resulting from the presence of ZnO nanowires was evident because control fracture surfaces showed significant fiber de-bonding or adhesive failure of the interface, while nanowire enhanced fracture surface showed failure that was dominated by cohesive failure of the matrix. This indicates that the ZnO nanowires have strong interaction with the carbon fibers. It should be noted that the lamina exhibits a lower strength increase than the single fiber test for several reasons, first the shear strength is a

different parameter than the interfacial strength and should naturally give different results, and second the lamina's failure is controlled by a number of factors including cohesive failure of the matrix and increased number of defects as the specimen becomes large.

The growth of the ZnO nanowires on the surface of carbon fibers leads to the formation of two interfaces one between the carbon and ZnO and a second between the ZnO and the polymer matrix. The increased interface strength resulting from the ZnO nanowires implies that both interfaces are stronger than the carbon and epoxy of a typical composite. The increased strength of the ZnO/polymer interface is attributed to increased bond area due to the high surface area of the nanowires, localized reinforcement of the matrix resulting from the penetration of the stiff nanowires into the matrix providing local reinforcement and enhanced load transfer between the fiber and matrix. The increased surface area and penetration into the matrix can be clearly seen in Fig. 5b-c which show the region where the carbon fiber separated from the ZnO nanowires and Fig. 5c shows a magnified image of the interfacial region of the fiber. The use of a rigid material is advantageous because flexible materials such as carbon nanotubes easily collapse around the fiber in the presence of a polymer matrix.^[4] It can be seen from these figures that the ZnO nanowires remain well bonded to the matrix and failure occurs at the ZnO / carbon fiber interface.

Figure 5. Results of v-notch shear testing performed to determine how the ZnO nanowires impact the lamina. (a) shear stress vs strain of the carbon fiber specimens and the ZnO nanowire coated carbon fiber specimens, (b) SEM image of the polymer surface after debonding from a ZnO coated carbon fiber (scale bar 5 μm) and (c) an enlarged image of the fiber edge showing the ZnO nanowires remaining in the polymer indicated debonding of the nanowires from the carbon fiber (scale bar 1 μm).

The results of our testing indicate that the carbon fiber bonds more strongly to the ZnO nanowires than to a composites grade epoxy. In order to characterize the interfacial region between the carbon fiber and nanowires, high resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM) images of the ZnO/carbon interface have been taken and are shown in Fig. 6a. The ZnO is polycrystalline at the interface due to the seeding process which deposits randomly oriented nanoparticles on the surface of the fiber from which the nanowires grow. The strong adhesion between the carbon fiber and ZnO nanowires is believed to be due to the presence of chemical bonding between the hydroxyl, carbonyl and carboxyl functional groups that are naturally present on the surface of carbon fibers. Many studies have been performed to identify the surface

functional groups on carbon fibers. Dilsiz and Wightman tested unsized AS4 carbon fiber and found the surface had functional groups with 20.2% hydroxyl, 9.2% carbonyl and 7.2% carboxylic acid surface coverage,^[29] the authors subsequently characterized unsized IM7 carbon fiber and found 20.1% hydroxyl, 2.3% carbonyl and 7.5% carboxylic acid functional groups on the fiber surface.^[30] The strength increase is attributed to the affinity of ZnO to these functional groups which is well documented in the literature. For instance the chemisorption of carbonyl on the surface of ZnO has been shown through both nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR)^[31] and IR spectroscopy^[32-33] and the chemisorption of hydroxyl groups through XPS analysis.^[34] It is also well documented that ZnO and carboxylic acid interact very strongly forming ionic bonding due to the electrostatic forces between Zn^{2+} and the polar acid.^[35-37] The strong bonding between ZnO and carboxylic acid has also been demonstrated on carbon nanotubes (CNTs) where the high level of control over lattice defects has allowed investigations into the affinity of ZnO for certain functional groups, with the results showing the greatest affinity for carboxylic acid.^[38-39] It is believed during the seeding process the ZnO nanoparticles self-assembly on the functional site of the carbon fiber leading to ionic bonding across the interface and greater adhesion than epoxy.

Figure 6. (a) HRTEM images of the ZnO-Carbon interface showing the amorphous carbon and polycrystalline ZnO and (b) electron energy loss spectroscopy of the interface showing the absence of chemical bonding at the interface.

While CNTs have been shown to interact very strongly with ZnO the spectroscopy results in the literature have not provide the sensitivity required to measure the ionic bonding.^[40-43] The chemisorption of the functional groups discussed before were quantitatively measured by bonding the group to the surface of the ZnO rather than bonding the ZnO to a secondary structure containing the functional groups. For instance the affinity of carboxylic acid to ZnO was measured by the adsorption of formic acid to the surface of ZnO nanoparticles.^[38] The later method is more difficult due to the large number of bonds away from the interface. We have also performed spectroscopic characterization of the interface through EELS as shown in Fig. 6b and Raman Spectroscopy shown in Fig. 7. Our EELS analysis was performed on the interface shown in Fig. 6a and like prior studies^[35] does not show the chemisorption of the functional groups in the measurements. However, its is believed that this is due to the relatively large amount of carbon and ZnO bonds which make the far smaller

number of ionic bonds present at the interface insufficient to show up in the measurement. The Raman analysis shown in Fig. 7 was performed on a $2\mu\text{m}$ spot of the bare carbon fiber, ZnO nanoparticles fabricated through the same process as the nanowires and the ZnO nanowires coated fibers. The Raman spectrum of the ZnO powder show excellent agreement with the published spectroscopy data for unoriented Zincite. It can be seen in Fig. 7 that the ZnO peaks appear in the coated fiber sample; however the intensity is low in comparison to the carbon peaks. The low intensity of the ZnO relative to the carbon fiber demonstrates that the local interaction between the carbon and ZnO at the interface would not be sufficient to be measured.

Figure 7. Raman spectrum of the ZnO power synthesized using the same solution process, bare carbon fibers and the carbon fiber with ZnO nanowires growth on the surface. The ZnO trace shows excellent agreement with the published unoriented zincite spectrum.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The novel ceramic ZnO nanowire interface developed here has been shown to offer a significant increase in the interfacial strength (increased by 113%) without degradation of the fiber strength. Prior techniques for the growth of secondary materials on the fiber to enhance load transfer have significantly reduced the fiber strength. Additionally through v-notch shear testing, this work has shown that the ZnO nanowires translate the improved interfacial properties to the lamina. Analysis of the surface following failure showed the bare carbon fiber samples were dominated by adhesive failure while the ZnO nanowire coated samples were predominantly cohesive matrix failure. It is believed that the ZnO has greater adhesion to the carbon fiber surface due to chemisorption of functional groups on the surface of the carbon fiber by the ZnO nanoparticles during seeding. Additionally, it was shown that the rigid nature of the ceramic nanowires allows them to penetrate into the matrix material to improve load transfer, increase surface area for bonding and functionally grade the interface. By functionally grading the interface, composites can be redesigned to emulate biological systems, which rarely exhibit discrete boundaries between two materials of vastly different mechanical properties. For example, the human musculoskeletal system exhibits gradients between bone, cartilage and muscle, reducing stress concentrations and exhibiting durability and life, far exceeding human-made mechanical systems. With the recent acceptance of composite materials in commercial aircraft, these results

could lead to significantly stronger and tougher materials which would advance the lifespan and safety of these structures. This fiber whiskerization technique can also be combined with recent advances in nanocomposite matrix materials to further increase the strength of the composite material.^[44,45] Additionally, the use of ZnO nanowires to increase strength and toughness of the composite may also lead to multifunctional composites using the semiconductive and piezoelectric properties of ZnO.

4. EXPERIMENTAL

Nanoparticle Growth: The formation of ZnO nanoparticles is carried out by dissolving zinc acetate dihydrate (0.0125M) in ethanol at 50°C under vigorous stirring. After cooling to room temperature, the solution is diluted with additional solvent to a concentration of 0.0014M. A 0.02M NaOH ethanol solution is similarly prepared at 60°C and after cooling is diluted to a concentration of 0.0057M. The two solutions are vigorously mixed at a growth temperature of 55°C at a volume ratio of 18:7 [19]. The resulting suspension of nanoparticles can then be coated onto the substrate through dip coating, spin coating or self assembly. For the untreated carbon fibers, ZnO nanoparticles were coated in the carbon fiber by means of dip coating, after which the carbon fibers were annealed at 150°C for 10 minutes to enhance adhesion between the fibers and the ZnO nano particles.

Nanowire Growth: ZnO NWs were grown using a hydrothermal method [21-23]. This process is as follows, an aqueous solution of zinc nitrate hydrate (0.025M) with hexamethylenetetramine (HMTA) (0.025M) was used as the solution for ZnO nanowire growth. The growth process was performed in a glass beaker with the solution temperature maintained at 90 °C for 4 hours on a hot plate [14]. The carbon fibers were rinsed with de-ionized water and dried at 100 °C in atmosphere after removal from the solution.

Single Fiber Tensile Testing: Testing was performed on two sets of fibers, carbon fibers used as received and carbon fibers with nanowires grown on the surface. For each set, eight fibers were tested. A sample of IM7 carbon fiber tow (5µm filament diameter) was used as the substrate for nanowire growth and the resulting ZnO nanowire geometry was 50nm diameter and 500nm length.

Epoxy Wetting: A small amount of epoxy was applied to the carbon fiber and cured. The carbon fiber, ZnO nanowires, and epoxy coating were then milled away using Nova 200 NanoLab UHR FEG-SEM/FIB such that the cross section of the fiber could be viewed. (Epon 862 resin and Epikure 9553 hardener from Hexion Specialty Chemicals (Houston, TX) blended at a resin to hardener weight ratio of 100:16.9)

Single Fiber Segmentation Testing: Single fiber composite specimens were fabricated by suspending a single filament of carbon fiber across a silicon mold that was infiltrated with a composites grade epoxy (EPON 863 resin and 9554 hardener from Hexion Specialty Chemicals (Houston, TX) blended at a resin to hardener weight ratio of 100:16.9). As the resin cures, compressive stresses can be induced in the fiber leading to bulking of the fiber and potentially limiting the ability to reach segmentation saturation before failure of the polymer specimen. Therefore the fiber was pre-strained during curing by suspending a 3.73 g weight from fiber during curing.

V-notch lamina testing: Separate composite laminate were fabricated from bare carbon fibers and carbon fibers with ZnO nanowires grown on the surface. The matrix material was EPON 862 resin and 9553 hardener from Hexion blended at a resin to hardener weight ratio of 100:16.9. Because the lamina are made from individual tows rather than woven fabric, the samples were cast in an aluminum mold of the appropriate dimensions with 1 MPa applied via external pressure and vacuum bagging. The samples were cured at room temperature for one hour following by one hour at 100°C and one hour at 160°C. The samples were measured to have a volume fraction of 50% using the technique defined in ASTM D3171.[46]

Electron microscopy, Raman Spectroscopy and TGA: SEM images were taken on a Hitachi S-4700 FESEM. TEM (HRTEM) images were obtained using a Phillips CM200-FEG TEM/STEM. Electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) was obtained on JEOL JEM-2010F TEM/STEM. Raman spectroscopy was obtained from a custom system with 532 nm excitation wavelength laser.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors of this work would like to gratefully thank Dr. Jeff Bauer and Dr. Qihong Zhang of the Composite Technologies Branch in the Materials and Manufacturing

Directorate of the Air Force Research Lab for performing single fiber tensile testing and Dr. Brett Williams of the Structures and Configuration Group of the NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory for assistance with the V-notch shear testing.

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